

The impact of TVET on growth and transformation in the manufacturing industries in Lao PDR

Skills for Industry Policy Brief Laos #3 (2023)

At a glance:

The Lao PDR manufacturing industry has grown rapidly in recent years, driven by domestic factors such as population growth, rising incomes, and changing consumer preferences. This growth has been accompanied by changes in individual businesses, such as new product offerings, adoption of new technologies, and strategic management decisions. Foreign direct investment in the agriculture sector has also played a role in the growth of the manufacturing industry. However, there are also challenges to the growth of the manufacturing industry, such as labor productivity issues:

- Foreign-invested factories require specific skills that domestic workers often lack, leading to dependence on foreign labor or production slowdowns.
- Compared to neighboring countries, wages in Laos are often not competitive, prompting skilled workers to migrate for better opportunities.
- There is a shortage of qualified employees in some industries, particularly in the food and beverage (F&B) sector.
- Companies are willing to consider applicants without any formal educational background or certifications if they have the necessary skills and experience.
- Some companies, particularly small factories, provide on-the-job training to upskill their employees.
- Larger companies are more selective in their hiring practices and may require a bachelor's degree or above for certain positions.

Upgrading a company's position in the value chain may be limited if it solely relies on upskilling its existing workforce. Investing in firm-specific skills may lead to underinvestment in more general, transferable skills. Overall, there seems to be little training taking place, and there are challenges related to access to graduates (small companies) and the quality and relevance of training (larger companies).

Situation of manufacturing industries in Laos:

According to the ASEAN Development Bank (2022), the primary reason for the remarkable economic growth in the Lao PDR has been the combination of capital investment and productivity growth. This is evident in the period between 2000 and 2019, where investment in natural resources played a vital role in the average annual GDP expansion of 7%. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the country experienced a 0.5% reduction in GDP growth in 2020, which also led to a surge in public debt, reaching 72% of GDP. The second wave of the pandemic also caused a delay in the expected 2.3% increase in real GDP growth in 2021 (ADB, 2022)¹. It is considered that the lack of educated and competent workers in Laos hinders the country's businesses from being more productive and competitive. However, the productivity level of Lao manufacturing firms is still relatively high compared to its regional peers although its labor productivity is poorer due to the low skilled laborers and low

1 ADB (2022). ASIAN DEVELOPMENT BANK MEMBER FACT SHEET. (<https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/27776/lao-2021.pdf>)

capital intensity (World Economic Forum 2018)². Lao manufacturing is less competitive overall in the region due to its poor worker productivity, which is 10% lower than Cambodia's and nearly half of Vietnam's (World Bank Group, 2018)³.

However, two-thirds of the industry has seen growth and transformation in the last five years. This suggests a shift towards a more diversified and productive sector; for instance, the garment industry is another major contributor to the manufacturing sector, providing employment opportunities and export earnings.

Despite the positive developments, the manufacturing sector still faces some challenges.

- **Low productivity and high production costs:** Many Lao manufacturing firms are small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) that use medium- or low-technology, leading to lower efficiency and higher costs.
- **Limited access to finance and markets:** SMEs often struggle to access the financing and market opportunities they need to grow and compete.
- **Lack of skilled labor:** The lack of skilled workers in key areas such as engineering, technology, and management is a major obstacle to the development of the manufacturing sector.
- **Weak infrastructure:** Poor infrastructure, including roads, electricity, and transportation networks, adds to the costs of doing business in Lao PDR.

Skills shortage in the manufacturing industries:

In many Lao PDR manufacturing industries, particularly in small and medium-sized factories, there is a common trend of employing workers with

2 World Economic Forum. 2018. Lao PDR: The Global Competitiveness Index 2017-2018 Edition. World Economic Forum, Geneva.
 3 World Bank Group. 2018. Doing Business in Lao PDR: Constraints to Productivity (English), World Bank Group, Washington DC

low levels of education. Operators typically come from a range of educational backgrounds, with about 28% of them having only primary education, as shown in Figure 1. This trend is particularly noticeable in garment factories, where there is preference for recruiting experienced workers who often possess minimal education. On the other hand, technicians and supervisors are typically more educated. In fact, 80% of these higher-level roles are held by people with at least a high school diploma. Large factories, which offer competitive wages, tend to attract more educated candidates.

Figure 1: Education of different occupation levels in the manufacturing industry

A report by Homesana in 2019 sheds light on the demographic profile of female garment workers in Lao PDR, indicating that they are typically young, unmarried migrants with limited prior experience and education.

The difficulty in recruiting qualified employees, especially evident in the F&B industry as shown in Figure 2, is not as significant as one might expect. This is likely due to several factors:

- Many companies prioritize hands-on skills and experience over formal education, especially for roles on the production line.
- Companies often provide on-the-job training to new hires, especially those from rural areas with limited education. For instance, in the garment industry, it is usual to recruit individuals with secondary education or less and train them on the job.
- Large-scale migration of Lao workers to Thailand has also impacted the labor market.

- There are significant differences between sectors and types of companies.
- Small factories tend to focus on upskilling their existing workforce rather than competing for the few qualified graduates.

Figure 2: Skills shortage (“During the last 5 years, was it difficult to find employees for your establishment meeting your requirements?”)

The managers expressed their willingness to consider applicants without any formal educational background or certifications, offering necessary on-the-job training when required.

“Education background is not our main concern. We emphasize experience and skills for the positions that they apply for; however, for operator positions, we don’t specify any criteria on qualification, including whether or not the applicant must have completed high school. Instead, the applicant should have the ability to operate a sewing machine.”

Vocational education and training status:

In Lao PDR, much like other developing nations, the manufacturing industry often employs individuals with limited education, providing them with on-the-job training. This trend is driven by several factors. Primarily, Lao PDR’s labor market is characterized by a significant portion of the population having minimal education, resulting in an abundant pool of potential workers with lower qualifications. Manufacturers typically hire these individuals for roles not necessitating extensive education, such

as entry-level or manual labor positions. For other roles, the companies provide workers on-the-job or induction training and upskilling to address the skills needs of companies. While pre-employment non-formal TVET training is rare for supervisor/technician employees (Figure 3), it is somewhat more common for operators. The latter group also benefits from greater opportunities for in-employment upskilling. A majority of both groups undergo initial induction training.

Figure 3: Training uptake in the manufacturing industries

Limited access to higher education or specialized vocational training in some areas of Lao PDR and outward migration to Thailand contribute to hiring trends, as discussed above. Keeping these factors in mind, it is still striking that most companies do not rely on the training provided by formal training providers, as illustrated by the small proportions of workers with pre-employment training.

Companies do not see their requirements met:

“Actually, we need mechanics with TVET knowledge and machinery working experience. Every year when we announce to look for new staff, I find many graduated students [from technical colleges], but most of them pass our standards. [They’re] poor in general knowledge, have lower grades, poor in English language, and are poor in soft skills. Thus we can’t get them”.

Another company operating in plastic manufacturing found that non-qualified employees often performed better after learning the tasks in the companies:

“There are two types. They might be TVET graduates or graduates from a higher secondary school. We will take them to train. Some don't have a certificate but they can do the work and improve themselves. Some people thought they have the knowledge, but when they come to work, they actually do not work well in our factory. Since 2010 we received lots of workers [from the technical colleges] but they are unsuccessful in our factory”.

Recommendations:

Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) can play a significant role in improving the quality of employees in Laos's industry. Here are some specific ways TVET can be applied to achieve this goal:

- 1. Align TVET curricula with industry needs:** Collaborate closely with industry partners to ensure that TVET curricula are up-to-date and aligned with the specific skills and competencies required by the industry. This can be achieved through industry-led curriculum development, internships, and apprenticeships.
- 2. Provide hands-on training and practical experience:** Integrate hands-on training and practical experience into TVET programs to equip graduates with the skills and knowledge they need to perform their jobs effectively. This can be achieved through partnerships with industry training centers, simulations, and real-world projects.
- 3. Promote TVET for upskilling and reskilling of existing workers:** Encourage and support companies to utilize TVET providers for upskilling and reskilling their existing workforce.

This can be achieved through government incentives, subsidized training programs, and tailored training packages for specific industry partnerships with industry training centers, simulations, and real-world projects.

- 4. Increase access to TVET for underserved groups:** Expand TVET opportunities for underserved groups, such as women, rural youth, and people with disabilities, to ensure that everyone has the opportunity to develop relevant skills and gain employment in the industry.
- 5. Enhance the quality and relevance of TVET instructors:** Provide professional development and training opportunities for TVET instructors to ensure they are equipped with the latest industry knowledge and teaching methodologies.
- 6. Strengthen TVET infrastructure and facilities:** Invest in upgrading TVET infrastructure and facilities to provide students with access to modern equipment, technology, and learning resources.
- 7. Promote TVET awareness and recognition:** Increase public awareness of the value and benefits of TVET to encourage more students to pursue TVET programs and employers to recognize TVET qualifications.
- 8. Develop TVET pathways for higher education:** Create seamless pathways for TVET graduates to transition to higher education, allowing them to further their studies and advance their care.

Sources:

- Homesana, Chanmala. 2019. “Understanding the Urban Livelihoods and Wellbeing of Migrant Women Working in Garment Factories in Vientiane, Lao PDR.”

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